

Verifying the Neighbouring k-edge Coloration Technique for Bipartite Graphs

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Abstract. This paper focuses on verifying the neighbouring k-edge coloration technique for balancing multi-color problems in the bipartite graph. Thus, it eliminates triangular copies of similar colour shades while maintaining exactly two colours spacing between the edges. It is achieved by inducing bipartite color selections from two unique color sets say U and V . Thus, ensures the minimum colour interference exists by employing a fair version of the neighbouring k-edge colouring technique. Theoretical evidence, theorems, and proofs are discussed, and results shows the superiority for equitable colourable of Wi-Fi applications.

Keywords: Bipartite color selections strategy, Chromatic k-Colouring, Minimum color-interference vertices, and Colour spectrum equity.

1. Introduction

To guarantee the robustness of the model used in the system design, modern technologies undergo extensive evaluation and testing under a variety of stress conditions. Instead of trying to verify each model in isolation in real time which is obviously impossible a stimulated graph is used to replicate the actual system response into a graph in which the characteristics changes can be identified during testing [1]. However, the stimulated graph does not provide a perfect reflection of response changes; this is because even subtle shifts in response would be reflected in the graph's parameters, which can be readily observed with the aid of a colour spectrum. This colour space is used in many models, with the vertices being given the appropriate colours. To implement this function, a suitable threshold point is identified, after which vertices in the graph are coloured in various ways [2]. There are a variety of different graph models and colour allocation strategies that can be used depending on the context of the application. Because of this, standardising the process of colour selection for the design of an entire system makes it hard to measure performance. Because using the same colour for multiple vertices creates an interference problem. Therefore, it causes a colour issue at the vertices of the threshold spectrum.

Neighbouring edge colouring is a sophisticated model that adjusts colour spectrum to user scales. This model reduces the edge total k colour in the colour spectrum. Wireless sensor network [3], surveillance network [4], and security attention [5] used graph theory to visualise unexpected changes and monitor pre-defined task function by observing chromatic colour spectrum variation in stimulated graph. This paper reduces similar colour occupancy over two closer vertices by internally adjusting the sub-graph vertices' threshold points. The symmetric matrix is used to set the instance threshold point for colouring vertices. By calculating the optimal threshold value for each vertex in the stimulated graph, F.S. Benevides et al were able to minimise interference between the vertices [1]. However, the internal adjustment of colour shades existing between two similar vertices is dependent on active participating vertices and the vertex thickness that is estimated. Let us consider a stimulated graph G_s , where the vertices each have a distinct colour scheme, with choices made from two distinct sets of colours: dark colours (U_i), and light colours (V_j). For each vertex in the graph, the values $\forall i = j = \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ denoted a different colour. To find the maximum number of vertices in a graph, we can ignore some of the vertices by using the notation $ex(k, f)$. Therefore, if there is a chance of forming a graph out of these vertices, then the colouring of their adjacent k-edges in an f -free neighbourhood vertices. By [2] solved that all vertices have the same colour, and that $k \geq l + 1$ is the minimum number of colours needed to fill in the entire graph, then f is satisfied by D. Clemens et al. Furthermore, graph partition is providing better balancing on the color selection as well as minimum interference. It is achieved by using the specific condition is given as $ex(k, f) = \lfloor k/2 \rfloor \cdot \lfloor k + 1/2 \rfloor$. Such graph is simply defined as external free graphs.

2. Preliminary:

- To ensure the system design model's robustness, we adapt the neighbouring edge colouring scheme by including a symmetric metric for thinking about the three types of stimulated graphs (3, 4, and 8-color graphs).
- The vertex's thickness is used as a replacement metric for counting the number of vertices needed for a critical mass to form during instance graph generation.
- An optimal vertex colouring of the G_s , where the range of colours allotted is computed as k for $v \in V(G_s)$, and the colours of the vertices are represented as $V_i = \{C_{v1}, C_{v2}, \dots, C_{vn}\}_{i=1,2,\dots,k}$ or otherwise $C_{vi} (1 = i = k)$. Color interference between adjacent vertices is minimised under the following conditions:

$$|C_{vi} - C_{vj}| = 1; |C_{vi} - C_{vj}| = k$$
- Adjusting the threshold limit without encountering colour interference at the vertices requires the fewest possible colour changes. Consequently, $\chi'_k(G_s)$ represents the fair representation of chromatic colouring along adjacent k -edges.

Figure 1 Shows tree structure of stimulated graphs with equitable edge colouring.

If the vertices in an f -free neighbourhood of a graph with k -edges allow colour combinations such that $C^{ex(k,f)}$, then the graph can be coloured arbitrarily. Author's name used this information to try to get the right balance between contrasting colours and induce just the right amount of colour shift. Similarly, C. Hoppen et al [6] proved the colour interference minimization for a limited set of conditions, such as $l = 2$ and $k = 6$. However, the number of active participating vertices and the range of colours available impact what colours should be chosen. In order to generate multipartite graphs with approximately higher contributions, the O. Pikhurko et al [7] investigated the necessary balancing conditions. Thus, it is useful in locating the optimal solution for producing multipartite graphs, free of the confounding effects of colour.

In particular, [8-12], who noted that the colours are dispersed at random outside of the usual colour spectrum, can absorb a wide variety of colour patterns. They found that using the same colour in multiple places was prohibited. For instance, in the case where $f = C_i, i = 1,2,3$ there are three possible colours scattered towards the same edge line colours, indicating a retained rainbow pattern between colours of the same hue. The maximum number of vertices in an f -free neighbourhood can be coloured in a monochromatic pattern where each edge is k in length.

1.1 Contribution:

In this paper, focuses on verifying the neighbouring k -edge coloration technique for balancing multi-color problems in the bipartite stimulated graph. Thus, it eliminates triangular copies of similar colour shades while

maintaining exactly two colours spacing between the edges.

The active participation vertices in the sub-graph selection are impacted by the multi-colour interference problem when a positive integer, say q , is varied linearly. To address this issue, let's imagine the function also involves fixing a positive integer such that a subgraph with k -edges and f -free neighbours can have adjacent k -colours in a specific pattern (P).

$$C_{q,f,P}(k) = \max_{\forall q} \{ |C_{q,f,P}(G_s)| : |V(G_s)| = k \}$$

This implies that the k -edge coloration of the G_s is required extreme observation of f and P externally. Such that if $C_{q,f,P}(G_s) = C_{q,f,P}(k)$. The primary goal is to enhance the multi-colour distribution of no interference of similar colour shades to neighbouring vertices and understand two colour patterns incorporated in the taken G_s .

The single G_s with 3-colouring and 4-colouring principle involves external graph considering $q = 2$ and $k = 6$ and $q = 3$ and $k = k_0$. The colour distribution is established overactive participant vertices is defined as

$$9^{6 \cdot k^2 / 4^2} = 27^{k^2 / 2^2} = 27^{ex(k,f)}$$

In other words, altering the colour shade sets like $C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k \rightarrow \{U\}_i$ and it would be applicable to beyond the expected levels. It is verified by combining the lemma using linear programming method.

3. Main Ingredients

Consider two main issues that are always present in the stimulated graph: (i) colour interference between neighbouring vertices [7] and (ii) difficulty adjusting the colour shades within a limited number of colours for broad applications [8,9]. Theoretically, we examine three distinct graphs to establish the theorem and its proof to comprehend the just manner of chromatic colour distribution among the vertices. Figure 1 shows a Tree-type stimulated graph that follows an equitable form of the neighbour edge colouring principle.

Lemma 1.1: For 3-colouring graph observers 2-unique pattern with exactly occupying the two classes and let be $3 = q = 12$. For every $k = k_0$ assigning proper colour shades of the G_s .

$$|C_{q,f',P}(G_s)| \leq q^{ex(k,f')}$$

Thus, it is valid only if G_s bipartite stimulated graph.

The stimulated graph, denoted by G_s is made up of vertices $V(G_s)$ and edges $E(G_s)$. Finite, loop, and multi-edged graphs are considered in this analysis. In [6], a colour class is defined as a set of vertices that share the same colour assignment. When the colour space is partitioned into k -nonempty independent vertices colour sets $C_v = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k\}$, such that $|V_i| - |V_j| = 1, \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Then this class is uniformly distributed across the colour space. If you have a graph G_s and you want to colour it fairly, you can do so by writing $?_e(G)$ [9]. Consequently, the degree of the vertices is evident in adjusting the colour index to each vertex of the graph, which is given by

$$?_{et}(G) = \min_{?_{i,j}} \{ k / ?_e(G_s) \} \text{ for } x? P_{V_i} = V_i? E_i, f(x) = i, i = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

Lemma 1.2: Consider the subgraph of G_s influence with chromatic colour shades $?_e(G) = l + 1 = 3$ and pattern observed indicated as P for f . This pair (f, P) satisfies the distribution of similar color stability over all positive integers q for $k = k_0$. Thus, $|C_{q,f',P}(G_s)| = q^{ex(k,f')}$ exist the $V(G_s) = V_1 \cup \dots \cup V_l$ under condition of $?_{i=1}^l V_i = dk^2$.

To reduce the effects of colour mixing, it is necessary to extract the local rainbow pattern and sort the extracted data into distinct classes. Keep in mind that local rainbow is also a factor in the 3-color graph.

Lemma 1.3: Consider if $l = 3$ and $P = 2$ of local rainbow patterns are extracted which is defined as (C_{l+1}, P) that satisfies the distribution of similar color stability over positive integer $q > e(l + 1)$. In such that every $k = k_0$ assigning proper colour shades at most of $q^{ex(k,C_{l+1})}$ holds (C_{l+1}, P) k -edge free neighbouring colours of G_s .

Proof: let $G_s = (V, E)$ be the bipartite graph, M and N be the subset of $V_i(G_s)$. If M and N be the non-empty

and edge density is computed between two subsets of same class by

$$d(M, N) = \frac{e(M, N)}{|M||N|}$$

The edge between two end points is denoted as $e(M, N)$. If $\epsilon > 0$ then pair (M, N) be the regular for every $x \in M$ and $y \in N$ which satisfies $|x| > \epsilon |M|$ and $|y| > \epsilon |N|$. Then, we have $|d(x, y) - d(M, N)| < \epsilon$.

This class is equitably distributed along the color spectrum where color scale is divided into k -non-empty independent vertices color sets $C_v = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k\}$, such that $|V_i| - |V_j| = 1, \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, k$.

Corollary 1: if $c_i = 3$ for any graph G_s , then $f(v)$ for each $v \in V(G_s)$ would be employed with chromatic k -edge colouring of G_s .

Corollary 2: if $c_i = 4$ for any graph G_s , then $f(v)$ for each $v \in V(G_s)$ would be employed with chromatic k -edge colouring of G_s .

4. PROVIDING LEMMA 1.1

In this section detail description of Lemma 1.1 by considering fixed number of positive integers $3 = q = 12$ for chromatic edge colouring distribution. To avoid confusion, we took only single case of $q = 6^3$.

To verify this assuming two independent auxiliary constants say $a > 0$ and $\beta > 0$ such that

$$a < \frac{a}{12}, q^{q\beta+h(qk)} < \left(\frac{q}{A(q)}\right)^a \text{ and } \beta < \frac{\delta}{2q} \quad (1)$$

Where, $A(q)$ be the linear distribution function over several variables and $h(a) = -a \log_2 a - (1-a) \log_2(1-a)$ be the entropy operator lies in the interval of 0 and 1. It is defined as

$$\binom{k}{\rho k} \leq 2^{H(\rho)k}$$

Where, $0 < \epsilon = 1/2$. Let $\epsilon = \epsilon(q, \beta, 3) > 0$ satisfy the assumption of Lemma 1.2 and without losing the generality of $\epsilon < \beta/2$.

When the colour space is partitioned into k -nonempty independent vertex colour sets, this group is spread out evenly across the visible spectrum. Where, $C_v = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k\}$, such that $|V_i| - |V_j| = 1, \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, k$. However, irregular pairs affect the chromatic colour distribution over similar colour shades. Hence,

$$q \cdot \binom{x}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{y}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{q^2}{2} \cdot k^2 = \frac{qk}{4} \cdot k^2 \quad (2)$$

Moreover, G_s has chance of occupying irregular pairs with similar colour shades. It is defined as

$$x \cdot \left(\frac{y}{x}\right)^2 = \frac{k^2}{x} \leq \epsilon k^2 \leq \frac{\beta}{2} \cdot k^2 \quad (3)$$

Let $H = H(\beta)$ is the cluster graph associate with multi-colour shades of the V_i and then boundary limit of selecting colour shades is defined as

$$\binom{k^2}{q\beta k^2} \cdot q^{q\beta k^2} \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^q i^{\epsilon_i(H)}\right) \left(\frac{y}{x}\right)^2 \leq 2^{h(q\beta)k^2} \cdot q^{q\beta k^2} \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^q i^{\epsilon_i(H)}\right) \left(\frac{y}{x}\right)^2 \quad (4)$$

Remember that in equation a is a constant that is not a part of any other expression (1).

Claim 1: If cluster group formed from multi-colour shades sets acquired minimum interference in G_s . Such that $e_{q-3}(H) + \dots + e_q(H) \geq ex(x, C_3) - \alpha x^2$

This claim is deserved only of H' associate with the subgraph with vertices sets of $V_{q-3} \cup \dots \cup V_q$. Based on

Lemma 1.3 provides partition result $U_1 \cup U_2 = [x]$ with

$$e_{H'}(U_1) + \dots + e_{H'}(U_2) \leq -\alpha x^2$$

Consider $\hat{H}$, said be the bipartite stimulated graph of H' along bipartition subset of $U_1 \cup U_2$ and satisfying all vertices presented.

$$e(\hat{H}) \geq ex(x, C_3) - 2\alpha x^2$$

Thus, it eliminates triangular copies of similar colour shades $E_1 \cup \dots \cup E_{q-4}$, while maintaining exactly two colours spacing between the edges. Suppose, if two vertices lies on similar colour shades which means $f \in C_{f_1} \cap C_{f_2}$. Then it checks the condition as $|C_{f_1} \cap C_{f_2}| = q - 1$, if it is verified then assign $|C_{f_1}| + |C_{f_2}| = 2q - 6 = q$. In such case, two-colour triangular property is Lemma 1.2 contradiction.

Proposition 1: There exists a constant chromatic k -edge colouring of given a graph G_s , a matrix element m , and a chromatic colour shade of size $|C_{v_i}| = 2$ endowed with a symmetric matrix of M of vertices colour interference.

Proof: Let I denote the current colour shades c_i , immediate neighbouring vertex colour interference, i.e. $I = \sum_{i \in V} M(C_{v_i}, c_i)$

Any vertex colouring is acceptable, if no two neighbouring vertices share the same colour. We assumed that every vertex in $v \in V(G_s)$ was assigned a positive integer by the function f . If the vertices of G sin are coloured using k -coloring, then V_i and V_j are very similar in colour. However, for any number of vertices in a graph, the bare minimum of colours is included to allow for chromatically fair allocation of colour shades without inducing neighbouring vertex colour interference. This can easily remember the notation $\sum_{f(G)}$, where G_s is the total k -core of the equitable form of neighbouring vertex colouring.

Proposition 2: For all element in subset of Q provides sufficient input to subgraph of H' occupy in the multi-colour graph with vertices

For a given graph G_s , any vertices color interference, if it is fixed number belong to $Q \in [q]$ and then minimum color selection is obtained by verifying the sub-graph threshold of $\sum_{i=2}^{q-4} V_i(Q, int_{=2}; H) \leq \sum_{i=q-3}^q V_i(H)$ triangular free.

Exists only two-element present in the subset of $Q \in [q]$ such that

$$|\sum_{i=2}^{q-4} V_i(Q, int_{\geq 2}; H)| \geq \sum_{i=2}^{q-4} \frac{\binom{q}{2} - \binom{q-1}{2}}{\binom{q}{2}} \cdot |V_i(H)| \tag{5}$$

There is existing inequality of the Proposition 1 which is stated as

$$\sum_{i=2}^{q-4} \frac{\binom{q}{2} - \binom{q-1}{2}}{\binom{q}{2}} \cdot e_i(H) + \sum_{i=q-3}^q e_i(H) \leq ex(x, C_3) \tag{6}$$

Proof: To satisfies the sub-graph threshold of $\sum_{i=2}^{q-4} V_i(Q, int_{=2}; H) \leq \sum_{i=q-3}^q V_i(H)$ triangular free. Consider that the size of each edge over colour distribution is equally.

We can add the sizes of the lists C_{f_1} , C_{f_2} , and C_{f_3} to get at least $(q - 3) + 4 = q + 1$ if one of the edges is in $q = q_3 \cdot E(H)$. The contradiction arises because two of the lists must share the colour, and the third list contains the equation (6), which results in a 2-colored triangle. Now, let's pretend that $C_{f_1}, C_{f_2}, C_{f_3} \in \sum_{i=2}^{q-4} V_i(Q, int_{=2}; H)$. Two of the lists must have the same colour, Q , since their sizes add up to at least three, and the third list has an element with the same colour, proving the first part of the Lemma 1.2.

5. CONCLUSION

The bipartite stimulated graph was shown to be the only n -vertex graph that maximises the number of k -edge-colourings without duplicating any triangles with exactly two colours. While the same method can be applied up

to $r = 12$. It is achieved by inducing bipartite color selections from two unique color sets if $l = 3$ and $P = 2$ of local rainbow patterns are extracted which is defined as (C_{l+1}, P) that satisfies the distribution of similar color stability over positive integer $q > e(l + 1)$. In such that every $k = k_0$ assigning proper colour shades at most of $q^{ex(k, C_{l+1})}$ holds (C_{l+1}, P) k -edge free neighbouring colours. Therefore, by employing a fair version of the neighbouring k -edge colouring technique, it is possible to guarantee that the optimised colour selection is present. Theoretical evidence, theorems, and proofs are discussed, and the results show that Wi-Fi applications are superior in terms of equitable color stability.

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